

Digital Literacy Skills and Service Delivery of Librarians in North-Central Public Universities, Nigeria

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Abstract

Keywords:

Library service delivery, Digital literacy skills, Librarians, library management

Introduction: Library service delivery facilitates interaction between librarians and library users to satisfy academic goals. Digital literacy skills (such as searching, accessing, locating, using, communicating, and evaluating information) can help to minimize poor library services. Therefore, this study investigated the influence of digital literacy skills on the service delivery of librarians in public universities in North-Central Nigeria.

Methodology: A survey research design was used for the study. The population comprised 274 professional librarians from 15 public universities in North-Central Nigeria. Total enumeration was used. A structured and validated questionnaire was employed to collect data from the respondents. The reliability of the constructs was confirmed using Cronbach's alpha, with coefficients ranging from 0.93 to 0.97. A response rate of 89.8% was achieved. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics at a 5% level of significance.

Findings: Digital literacy skills had a significant influence on service delivery ($\text{Adj.}R^2 = 0.423$, $F(6, 240) = 30.921$, $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that digital literacy skills enhanced the service delivery of librarians in public universities in North-Central Nigeria.

Conclusion/Recommendations: It was recommended that the library management of public universities in North-Central Nigeria should sustain the high level of service delivery. Additionally, they should ensure continuous improvement of the digital skills of librarians for effective service delivery.

Introduction

Service organizations could be seen as that part of the economy that create services instead of goods. Hence, the activities coming from the provider or rendered to anyone in need of it could be regarded as service delivery. Organizations have to measure how effective these services are because it is associated with how well or poorly the organizations are performing in relation to the services provided. As noted by Gaitho (2017) and Akanmidu (2021), service delivery refers to the process of providing and delivering a service to customer or clients. It involves the activities and steps taken to ensure that a service is delivered efficiently and effectively to meet the needs and expectations of recipients.

Public service delivery is designed around the needs and welfare of the citizens. Most public delivery systems are marred by delays, lack of transparency, and varied inefficiencies. Any organization that is aimed at providing services to the public should deliver it efficiently and effectively such that the customers will be satisfied. This is due to not rendering service on time is as good as the services not being delivered to the intended beneficiaries as it fails to meet the expectations of the beneficiaries (Sapru, 2020).

Onuoha and Chukwueke (2019) assert that service delivery in the library is equally a crucial component in evaluating the productivity and efficacy of librarians in academic libraries. University libraries are set up concurrently with the parent institution to assist the community's teaching, learning, and research efforts by offering timely and relevant information. The library accomplishes this purpose through gathering, organizing, preserving, and sharing information with the

community and its parent organization. As a result, university libraries, according to Adeniran (2011), are service-oriented businesses created to address the information demands of their customers by offering pertinent information resources and services. For Akanmidu (2021), library service delivery is divided into two main categories which are the technical and the customer services. Other scholars also believe that library services delivery can be divided into traditional and advanced categories.

Service delivery will be assessed using the indicators identified by Parasuraman et al. (1985), namely tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. However, evidence from literature as noted by Agoh et al. (2021) has revealed low level of service delivery and these are resulted from inadequate information materials, obsolete resources, epileptic power supply, poor funding, inadequate infrastructure, poor policies and facilities, inadequate operational systems and strategies for service delivery. Similar challenges may be facing the delivery of effective library services by librarians in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria. In view of these factors, this study examined the roles of technology use in improving or enhancing service delivery universities in North-Central public, Nigeria. The ability to accomplish these could be determined by the digital literacy skills of the librarians.

Literacy literally means being able to read and write, but when applied to libraries, it means having the skills to locate, comprehend, interpret, create, communicate, and compute utilizing printed and written materials connected to various contexts in the library. To attain goals, develop knowledge and potential, and be able to fully participate in the context in which they find themselves, people need to

have a continuum of learning that literacy provides (Montayo, 2018). As a result, it is expected of librarians to be digitally literate so that they can actively participate and learn the digital knowledge and skills required in the course of their service delivery to the university community.

Oriogu et al. (2017) define digital literacy as a set of abilities that enable people to successfully complete information retrieval tasks in technology contexts. According to the American Library Association (2013), using technology for tasks including finding, evaluating, creating, and communicating information necessitates the application of both cognitive and technical skills. Digital literacy skills are needed in libraries because the development and use of technologies are affecting the way information professionals work and repackage information in the digital age. Academic library services have changed, and new digital technologies like smartphones, tablets, desktops, and laptops have encouraged creativity. With the development of new technology, libraries are evolving into a variety of formats, such as electronic or virtual/digital libraries, which has an impact on how library professionals' jobs are changing. According to Kaeophanuek et al. (2018), being digitally literate is having the ability to use digital technology to gather, manage, integrate, process, and synthesize information. For the purposes of this study, Eisenberg and Berkowitz's (1990) six (6) ideas of information literacy which are task definition, information seeking (search), find, access, synthesis (evaluation), and use, were employed as the foundation for the digital literacy skills indicators.

Statement of the Problem

The major role of academic librarians is to provide efficient and adequate service in support of the research, teaching and learning functions of their users. However, literature and

observation have shown low level of services being delivered in the library. This is evidenced by uncomfortable infrastructure, inadequate staff strength, unskilled staff, and inadequate space (Udem et al., 2020). In addition, Awujoola and Omorinkoba (2021) pointed out issues such as the impatience and the unwillingness of the librarians to assist information seekers, harshness and unpleasant attitude of librarians. There is also low service delivery in Nigerian libraries due to obsolete library resources and librarians' disposition to service (Abdulsalami & Efosa, 2020). However, factors such as digital literacy skills of librarians may also contribute to the level of service delivery in public universities in North-Central Nigeria. In view of the fact that scholars have studied digital literacy skills independently, there is a dearth of literature with regards to the combined influence of digital literacy skills on service delivery of librarians in North-Central public university libraries in Nigeria. Therefore, it is on this premise that this study investigated the influence of digital literacy skills on service delivery of librarians in North-Central public universities in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised based on the objectives of the study:

1. What is the perception of librarians' service delivery in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of digital literacy skills possessed by librarians in North-Central public universities, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H01: Digital literacy skills have no significant influence on service delivery of librarians

in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria.

Service Delivery

Lovelock and Wright (2002) define service delivery as the act of genuinely giving a service or a product to a client or clients. In order to determine whether a service is rendered to a client in a fair or unfair manner, consideration must be given to the location, time, and mode of delivery. According to Rae et al. (2016), service delivery is a business component that defines the supplier-customer relationship. The provider offers services that could increase or decrease in value, such as tasks or information. Conversely, service delivery is defined as the discrepancy between the results of the delivery and the expectations of the consumer over the services they received. When an organization's service meets the expectations of its clientele, that customer perceives the service as having been effectively given; if not, the service is perceived as having been poorly delivered.

Although there are regional variations in the effectiveness of services provided, tangibility, dependability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy are the main factors influencing service effectiveness (Parasurman et al., 2014). The "how" and "what" of service design are defined by the "service concept," which helps to mediate between customer preferences and company strategic goals (Goldstein et al., 2002). According to Olanlokun (2013), service delivery is the effort a librarian puts to enable results for each user's query and meet their overall information needs. This effort can be made both inside and outside of the boundaries of the resources that are already available. According to research, university libraries provide a variety of services, including user education, interlibrary loans, abstracting, cataloging, reprographics, bibliographic services, circulation, reference, and information services (Olanlokun, 2013).

A library is essential to the university's ability to fulfill its academic mission because it offers resources to support teaching, research, and learning. A variety of services are requested of university librarians from their clients. Delivering documents, releasing information only when necessary, notifying customers about library updates, and providing reference services are just a few of the services provided. Various library services that promote research, education, and community services are actively managed by librarians, according to the literature (Ajayi et al., 2013; Aina, 2014). As technology advances, the ways that these services are supplied change quickly. The majority of these services were provided in the traditional manner, which required customers to visit actual libraries to access items or have materials distributed to their homes. But with the various Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in place, such services might be virtually provided through various platforms like email and social media. In order to efficiently provide library services to their consumers, librarians are expected to upgrade themselves in order to accomplish these ICT-inclined tasks. Mabawonku (2017) and Agbo and Eyinnah (2022) both support the relevance of ICT-embedded services and their use by librarians to increase their efficiency in carrying out various library operations.

Digital Literacy Skills

The concept of digital literacy skills is growing in importance in academic libraries due to the expansion of digital libraries and the digitalization of information sources. Different writers have offered different interpretations of what digital literacy is. Hague and Williamson (2016) define technical procedural, cognitive, and emotional-social skills as components of digital literacy. The American Library Association (2017) states that digital literacy is the conversion of printed text to a new type of literacy known as digitally mediated; it has features such as interactivity and openness that,

when embraced by students, have a positive impact on their use of libraries and, ultimately, on their academic productivity. Digital literacy, as defined by Paulina (2019), is the capacity to access, manage, integrate, analyze, produce, and disseminate information through the use of digital technology, communications tools, and/or networks. She also states that digital literacy is an essential element of joining a knowledge society.

The phrase digital literacy, in the words of Buckingham (2006:3) is "a combination of skills and knowledge that enable humans to efficiently carry out information retrieval activities in a technology-dominated environment such as digital libraries." Anyaoku (2012) claims that the capacity to use the internet, computer communication networks, network, and possess Web 2.0 abilities are essential for library workers' survival. Sani and Musa (2019) suggest that an individual with digital literacy abilities will remain in demand, whereas professional information workers lacking these skills would eventually become outdated. This demonstrated how important it is for staff workers to have exceptional digital literacy skills if they want to make a difference in a new library setting.

Because it is their responsibility to pass on knowledge to library customers from one generation to the next, university librarians must constantly improve their digital literacy abilities. Among them are word processing (for

example, registering library users), database searching (again for the purpose of selectively disseminating information), sending emails with attachments (for class assignments and research assistance), and web searching for data. According to Quadri and Garaba (2019), librarians with ICT abilities provide their clients with better up-to-date services. Additionally, they confirmed that the ICT proficiency levels of their respondents allowed for information sharing among colleagues for the delivery of more efficient library services. The success of ICT applications to contemporary libraries around the world is largely dependent on the digital literacy abilities held by professional librarians. According to Claro et al. (2012), ICT skills are those that include the whole capacity to address issues relating to information, communication, and knowledge technologies in the digital environment.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design. The population for this study comprised professional librarians in all the federal and state universities in North-Central Nigeria. In North-Central Nigeria, there are 15 public universities comprising eight (8) Federal universities and seven (7) State universities with 274 professional librarians. The sample size for this study was determined with total enumeration. This was used because of the small size of the population of librarians.

Table 1.0 Population and Sample Size of librarians in Federal and State Universities in North-Central, Nigeria

S/N	Universities and Location	Ownership	Professionals Librarians
1.	University of Ilorin	Federal	24
2.	University of Jos	Federal	34
3.	Federal University of Technology Minna	Federal	30
4.	University of Abuja	Federal	26
5.	Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Markurdi, Benue State.	Federal	37

6.	Federal University Lokoja, Kogi State	Federal	14
7.	Federal University, Lafia, Nasarawa State	Federal	10
8.	Federal University of Health Sciences, Otukpo, Benue State	Federal	4
9.	Benue State University, Makurdi	State	22
10.	Kogi State University, Anyigba	State	20
11.	Nasarawa State University, Keffi	State	15
12.	Plateau State University, Bokkos	State	4
13.	Ibrahim Babangida University, Lapai, Niger State	State	15
14.	Kwara State University, Ilorin	State	15
15.	Confluence University of science and Technology Osara, Kogi State	State	4
TOTAL			274

Source: Field Survey Results, 2023

Source: Librarians’ Record from the University Librarians Offices

A questionnaire titled “Digital Literacy Skills and service delivery” was used as the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire consisted mostly of closed-ended questions where the questions had options that were determined by the researcher and one open-ended question where respondents were required to respond in writing. The questionnaire was divided into section B measured the extent of service delivery using a scale ranging from: Strong Agree (4); Agree (3); Disagree (2); Strongly Disagree (1). Section D contained items on digital literacy skills in the public universities using a scale with response ranging from Very High (4); High (3); Low (2); and Very Low (1).

To ensure validity, questions, were based on information gathered during the literature review. It was validated for face and content validity by experts in the library and information science field. For the reliability of the instrument, the researcher conducted pilot study and the result of the Cronbach’s Alpha test determined the reliability of the main constructs in the survey. Instrument-digital

literacy skills and service delivery. The reliability test estimated the consistency of people’s responses to the items within a scale and the value. (<0.6) is adequate for the study (Hair, Tatham, Black, Babin & Anderson, 2014). The Cronbach alpha coefficient values for the variables were (Section B: Service delivery=0.96), and (Section D: Digital Literacy Skills Scale =0.97). The reliability results for the variables are all accepted for the study since their reliabilities are greater than 0.6, the minimum acceptable reliability for a research instrument.

The researcher administered the corrected copies of the questionnaire to the respondents in the study sample areas. The data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, the mean and standard deviation and inferential statistics would analyse the research questions in this study. Regression analysis was used to establish the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Analysis of closed-ended questions from the questionnaire was coded and analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Science Software (SPSS Version 25).

Result of Findings

Research Question One: **What is the perception of librarians’ service delivery in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria?**

Table 2.0 Perception of Librarians’ Service Delivery

Librarians’ Service Delivery	Strongly agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly disagree (1)	Mean	Std.
Empathy					3.47	0.532
I give attention to users concerns.	135 (54.9%)	106 (43.1%)	5 (2.0%)	0	3.53	0.539
I treat users with respect	132 (53.7%)	113 (45.9%)	1 (0.4%)	0	3.53	0.508
I demonstrate understanding of specific needs	119 (48.4%)	125 (50.8%)	2 (0.8%)	0	3.48	0.516
I ensure that user’s opinion is valued	113 (45.9%)	130 (52.8%)	3 (1.2%)	0	3.45	0.522
Librarians understand the users feelings	101 (41.1%)	133 (54.1%)	12 (4.9%)	0	3.36	0.574
Responsiveness					3.43	0.521
Librarians are always willing to help users	153 (62.2%)	91 (37.0%)	2 (0.8%)	0	3.61	0.504
I respond to users’ information request with courtesy	103 (41.9%)	140 (56.9%)	3 (1.2%)	0	3.41	0.516
I ensure that users information needs are treated with utmost efficiency	100 (40.7%)	145 (58.9%)	1 (0.4%)	0	3.40	0.500
I respond to users request for information as expected	91 (37.0%)	153 (62.2%)	2 (0.8%)	0	3.36	0.498
I respond to users request within an acceptable time frame	96 (39.0%)	144 (58.5%)	2 (0.8%)	4 (1.6%)	3.35	0.585
Tangibles					3.40	0.613
I ensure neatness of the library environments for library users	165 (67.1%)	80 (32.5%)	0	1 (0.4%)	3.66	0.499
I arrange books on display racks for users’ awareness	126 (51.2%)	110 (44.7%)	9 (3.7%)	1 (0.4%)	3.47	0.590
I ensure orderly arrangements of catalogue cards entries for users’ access	110 (44.7%)	122 (49.6%)	5 (2.0%)	9 (3.7%)	3.35	0.701
I ensure that infrastructures are adequate for the library users	97 (39.4%)	133 (54.1%)	15 (6.1%)	1 (0.4%)	3.33	0.606
I provide up-to-date computer equipment for information retrieval	83 (33.7%)	130 (52.8%)	32 (13.0%)	1 (0.4%)	3.20	0.668
Assurance					3.39	0.511

I assure users access to available information resources	113 (45.9%)	131 (53.3%)	2 (0.8%)	0	3.45	0.515
I assure users of prompt delivery of information resources in requested format	111 (45.1%)	134 (54.5%)	1 (0.4%)	0	3.45	0.506
I assure users of the relevance of information provided	91 (37.5%)	155 (63.0%)	0	0	3.37	0.484
I assure that users are convenient with the service provided	91 (37.0%)	154 (62.6%)	1 (0.4%)	0	3.37	0.491
I assure that users have the needed knowledge to instill confidence in them	86 (35.0%)	150 (61.0%)	9 (3.7%)	1 (0.4%)	3.30	0.557
Reliability					3.37	0.513
I treat users' information needs promptly	117 (47.6%)	122 (49.6%)	7 (2.8%)	0	3.45	0.553
I provide sufficient information needs of users	111 (45.1%)	135 (54.9%)	0	0	3.45	0.499
I deliver users request as promised	109 (44.3%)	131 (53.3%)	6 (2.4%)	0	3.42	0.542
I deliver error-free information to users	70 (28.5%)	170 (69.1%)	6 (2.4%)	0	3.26	0.492
I speedily correct wrongly posted users information	69 (28.0%)	173 (70.3%)	4 (1.6%)	0	3.26	0.477
Grand Mean					3.41	0.538

Source: Field Survey Results, 2023

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2023

Decision Rule: 1.0-1.74 = Strongly disagree; 1.75-2.49 = Disagree; 2.50-3.24 = Agree; 3.25-4.0 = Strongly agree

Table 2.0 presents the result on the perception of librarians on service delivery in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria. The table revealed that the librarians strongly agreed that service delivery was high with a grand mean of $\bar{x} = 3.41$, $SD = 0.538$ on a 4-point Likert-type scale. This implies that the

librarians deliver library services with empathy, responsiveness, reliable, tangible and with assurance. Going by the parameters measuring librarians' service delivery, the results revealed that empathy had the highest, which implies that their service delivery was good with an average mean of $\bar{x} = 3.47$, $SD = 0.537$, while reliability had the lowest, which implies that their service delivery was not as good with an average mean of $\bar{x} = 3.37$, $SD = 0.513$.

Research Question Two: **What is the level of digital literacy skills possessed by librarians in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria?**

Table 3.0 Digital literacy skills of librarians

Digital Literacy Skills	Very high (4)	High (3)	Low (2)	Very low (1)	Mean	Std.
Ability to Search					3.35	0.670
My ability to search the Internet for information is	125 (50.8%)	118 (48.0%)	1 (0.4%)	2 (0.8%)	3.49	0.555
My ability to search online databases for information is	118 (48.0%)	105 (42.7%)	19 (7.7%)	4 (1.6%)	3.37	0.698
My search engine ability is	104 (42.3%)	113 (45.9%)	21 (8.5%)	8 (3.3%)	3.27	0.753
My ability to search by date is	92 (37.4%)	130 (52.8%)	20 (8.1%)	4 (1.6%)	3.26	0.674
Ability to Use					3.33	0.635
My ability to utilize the library information to solve a problem is	116 (47.2%)	125 (50.8%)	1 (0.4%)	4 (1.6%)	3.43	0.594
My ability to utilize online public access catalogue (OPAC) is	98 (39.8%)	132 (53.7%)	14 (5.7%)	2 (0.8%)	3.33	0.619
My ability to utilize library information to make a decision is	93 (37.8%)	144 (58.5%)	3 (1.2%)	6 (2.4%)	3.32	0.624
My ability to utilize library databases to render services is	87 (35.4%)	131 (53.3%)	22 (8.9%)	6 (2.4%)	3.22	0.704
Ability to Communicate					3.32	0.609
My ability to communicate with my colleagues efficiently is	118 (48.0%)	122 (49.6%)	2 (0.8%)	4 (1.6%)	3.44	0.601
My ability to communicate the information to others in appropriate format is	92 (37.4%)	143 (58.1%)	5 (2.0%)	6 (2.4%)	3.30	0.633
My ability to communicate with users efficiently is	85 (34.6%)	153 (62.2%)	3 (1.2%)	5 (2.0%)	3.29	0.596
My ability as a librarian to communicate in real time is	82 (33.3%)	151 (61.4%)	9 (3.7%)	4 (1.6%)	3.26	0.606
Ability to Locate					3.30	0.616
My ability to locate information on books is	100 (40.7%)	133 (54.1%)	13 (5.3%)	0	3.35	0.579
My ability to locate information on the web is	91 (37.0%)	135 (54.9%)	20 (8.1%)	0	3.29	0.608
My ability to locate information efficiently is	85 (34.6%)	151 (61.4%)	6 (2.4%)	4 (1.6%)	3.29	0.594
My ability to locate information on the Internet is	95 (38.6%)	126 (51.2%)	21 (8.5%)	4 (1.6%)	3.27	0.683
Ability to Access					3.31	0.668

My ability to access information resources is	114 (46.3%)	111 (45.1%)	15 (6.1%)	6 (2.4%)	3.35	0.706
My ability to provide quick access to information resource to users is	95 (38.6%)	143 (58.1%)	2 (0.8%)	6 (2.4%)	3.33	0.620
My ability to ethically access information is	91 (37.0%)	146 (59.3%)	3 (1.2%)	6 (2.4%)	3.31	0.621
My ability to access the library databases is	96 (39.0%)	125 (50.8%)	17 (6.9%)	8 (3.3%)	3.26	0.725
Ability to Evaluate					3.24	0.650
My ability to evaluate website is	87 (35.4%)	129 (52.4%)	24 (9.8%)	6 (2.4%)	3.21	0.713
My ability to evaluate critically if the information collected is credible is	87 (35.4%)	141 (57.3%)	12 (4.9%)	6 (2.4%)	3.26	0.660
My ability to evaluate if the information is timely is	69 (28.0%)	167 (67.9%)	4 (1.6%)	6 (2.4%)	3.22	0.591
My ability to evaluate information obtained from different sources is	84 (34.1%)	148 (60.2%)	8 (3.3%)	6 (2.4%)	3.26	0.637
Grand Mean					3.31	0.641

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2023

Decision Rule: 1.0-1.74 = Very low; 1.75-2.49 = Low; 2.50-3.24 = High; 3.25-3.99 = Very high

The result in Table 3.0 shows the level of digital literacy skills possessed by librarians in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria. The grand mean $\bar{x} = 3.31$, SD = 0.641 on a 4-point Likert-type scale indicates that the level of digital literacy skill of the librarians is very

high. This implies that to a very high level, the librarians have the ability to access, locate, search, use, communicate and evaluate information. The result further reveals that the librarians’ ability to search had the highest mean of $\bar{x} = 3.35$ on a 4-point Likert-type scale while ability to evaluate had the lowest mean of $\bar{x} = 3.24$ on a 4-point Likert-type scale.

Hypothesis One: Digital literacy skills have no significant influence on service delivery of librarians in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria

Table 4.0: Simple linear regression analysis of digital literacy skills and service delivery

Predictors	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	T	P	R ²	Adj. R ²	F	ANOVA (Sig.)
(Constant)	2.152	0.111		19.372	0.000			131.146	
Digital Literacy Skills	0.381	0.033	.591	11.452	0.000	0.350	0.347		0.000

Dependent Variable: Service Delivery

Predictor: (Constant), Digital Literacy Skills

DF (F-Statistic) = 1, 245

DF (T-Statistic) = 244

Source: Field Survey Results, 2023

The result in Table 4.0 reveals that the independent variable has a positive coefficient, which is an indication that digital literacy skills positively influence service delivery of librarians in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria ($R^2 = 0.350$, $\beta = 0.591$, $t(244) = 11.452$, $p < 0.05$). The regression output revealed that digital literacy skills predictor variable is significant because $p < 0.05$. The result further shows an R^2 value of 0.350 which reveals that there is a 35.0% positive influence of digital literacy skills on service delivery. The $\beta = 0.591$ and $t(244) = 11.452$ is statistically significant at $p < 0.05$, this further gives the empirical evidence that digital literacy skills had significant influence on service delivery. Since p -value of digital literacy skills of librarians is below 0.05, hence the null hypothesis which states that digital literacy skills have no significant influence on service delivery of librarians in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Research question two sought to find the perception of librarians' service delivery in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria. The result revealed that the librarians strongly agreed to the perceptions held in their service delivery. This implies that the librarians deliver library services with empathy, responsiveness, reliable, tangible and with assurance. The result of this study confirmed the findings of Martins and Ledimo (2015) who discovered that workers in this government agency appeared to view service delivery innovation favorably within their organization. However, the result of this study contradicts the findings of Egunjobi et al (2022) and Amaechi et al. (2018) who all reported that library service delivery is low.

Research question two sought to know the level of digital literacy skills possessed by librarians in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria. The result indicates that the level of digital

literacy skill of the librarians is very high. This implies that to a very high extent, the librarians have the ability to access, locate, search, use, communicate and evaluate information. The result further reveals that the librarians have the ability to search, while ability to evaluate had the lowest. This finding is in line with the studies of Osinulu (2021), the findings revealed that library officials had a high degree of proficiency using digital technologies and were digitally literate. On the other hand, the result of this study did not agree with the findings of Chukwueke and Idris (2023), who found that there is a non-significantly low correlation between the staff members' digital literacy abilities and the services provided by academic libraries in Taraba State, Nigeria

The analysis of the hypothesis testing shows that digital literacy skills positively influenced service delivery of librarians in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria. These findings corroborate the finding of Adedara et al (2022) who discovered that in the field of their expertise, librarians possess both basic and intermediate technology proficiency. However, Idiodi and Emezaivwakpor (2022) did not find a significant influence between technology skills for information science professionals and its profitability to library services delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study analyzed the influence of digital literacy skills on service delivery of librarians in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria. The study established that librarians and library users alike agreed that there was effective service delivery in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria. The study also discovered that digital literacy skills enhanced service delivery. Additionally, it was revealed that librarians are digitally literate. digital literacy skills also had significant influence on service delivery of librarians in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria. By this, the study tends to be

successful as the objective has been achieved. Finally, this study concludes that there was a combined significant influence of digital literacy skills on service delivery of librarians in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria.

Recommendation

The following were recommended

1. Though, the study showed a high level of service delivery among librarians in public universities in North-Central, Nigeria, nevertheless, there is always room for improved services among librarians.
2. The study revealed that digital literacy skills contributed significantly to service delivery. Thus, this study recommends that the library management should continue to give more attention to digital literacy skills of librarians and ensure feedback mechanism for better performance.

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